

INDIVIDUAL, COMMUNITY, AND MODERNIST PERSPECTIVES ON 'ORI' AND 'CHI' IN YORUBA AND IGBO CULTURES

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19231161>

Keywords

*Ori; Chi;
Individual;
Community;
Modernist*

Abstract: *Ori (Yoruba) and Chi (Igbo) concepts symbolise the metaphysical connexion between the human and the divine. They act as guardians, spiritual duple, and life-blueprints. The study examined how Ori and Chi have influenced the development of individualism and moral responsibility within Yoruba and Igbo cultures. Hence, a Phenomenological theory was utilised in its discourse, while the phenomenological design was adopted to capture the perceptions and essential logics in the Yoruba and Igbo cultural milieu. Accordingly, a purposive sampling technique was applied to choose two key informed participants for an in-depth interview. This ensured that all the identified research themes were treated through the generated data. It was found out that Yoruba Ori is the vessel of personality and the individual personal deity, whereas the Igbo Chi is considered as a personal god or guardian spirit that acts as a spiritual double that validates a person's life-path. Ori, can influence an individual's destiny, while the Igbo agency espouses that Chi is sensitive to a person's struggles and life-direction that a person decides to follow. However, immorality cannot be attributed to Ori or Chi because in Yoruba belief, a criminal falls short of being an Omoluabi (ideal person), and In Igbo worldview, the person remains accountable for any determined action. Modernism and religion, have subverted the concepts of Ori and Chi, but these concepts must have been invented as tools deployed for social order. These could be primordial and atavistic concepts that leverages on modernism. In conclusion, Ori and Chi are metaphysical frameworks that are well-designed for individual accountability.*

Introduction: The Metaphysical Foundations of Ori and Chi

In the Yoruba and Igbo cosmologies, the thoughts on Ori and Chi function as the

ontological bases for understanding and appreciating human life and predestination. In Yoruba worldview, and within its metaphysical frameworks, Ori, is literally explained as the inner

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Advance Journal of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences

Adv. J. Arts. Hum. & Soc Sci.

Volume: 9; Issue: 02

March- April, 2026

ISSN 6300-5290

E-ISSN 4226-6348

Impact Factor: 7.80

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.net/ajahss/index.php/ajahss/index>

head, which has been theorised as an individual's divine essence and the principal seat of destiny (Gbadegesin, 1991). Within this social-spiritual milieu of the Yoruba tradition, *Orí* holds deep connotation as it is viewed as the guiding force that shapes destiny, reality, and individual identity. Indeed, it serves as a kind of conduit between the individual and the divine, bringing insight, direction, and spiritual protection on human existence (Fadesiye, 2024). *Ori* is thought to be a pre-birth nominated life-blueprint that largely shapes a person's existence, and the paths of life (Abimbola, 1971). It is implied to be the crown of the head that serves as a direct spiritual divine link, which functions as a person's peculiar deity that determines worldly choices (Makinde, 1985).

Fundamental to the Igbo spirituality and cosmology, the concept of *Chi* exemplifies a person's individual spirit or guardian deity that follows the person from birth (Achebe, 1975). *Chi* is intricately connected with *Eke*, a supporting spiritual force, and both are linked with natural creation. In that regard, *Chi* constitutes the basis of the Igbo's intelligence or astuteness, and provides a reasonable explanation for the varieties of human personality and the wide classification of causation (Chukwukere, 1983). Thus, since *Chi* is measured as a deific companion, facilitator, and mediator or intermediary between reality and the transcendental, it stands as an arbiter of a person's fortune and spiritual growth (Kanu, 2021). In other words, individual *Chi* is tantamount to the authentic self (Nze, 2024).

Correspondingly, it is observed that both concepts, albeit different in their cultural contexts, are based on the fact that human life is not inadvertently lived, but are unavoidably divinely connected. Hence, they bridge the physical and the transcendental realms (Nwobi, 2021). These elucidations show that *Ori* and *Chi* in the Yoruba and Igbo worldviews symbolise a kind of metaphysical and philosophic constructs that explain the solid association between the human and the divine. This explains why in Yoruba thought, *Ori*, is abstracted as an individual's divine inner core, selected at birth in the presence of *Olodumare* (the Supreme Being), and *Chi*, within the Igbo concept, is described as a personal god that functions as the spirit-double or guardian angel that governs an individual's life-trajectory from birth. They are like a 'spiritual GPS' that continually navigate life journey (Olugboji, 2023).

By examining these concepts, this paper tries to illuminate on how Yoruba and Igbo cultures frame divine authority with human destiny and life's journey.

Literature Review

Concept of *Ori* (Yoruba) and *Chi* (Igbo)

In Nigerian cosmology, *Ori* (Yoruba) and *Chi* (Igbo) represent the metaphysical connexion between the human and the divine that act as guardians, spiritual identities and life-blueprints. While *Ori* is considered as an intermediary between every man and the divinity he worships, it is also his personal divinity and regulates life to align with the

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wishes of the divine (Abimbola, 1975). Conversely, Nze (2024) stress that Chi is in everyone and no Chi is smaller or superior than the other. What this suggests, according to Achebe (2014), is that in the world in which humans exist, everyone has his or her double and equivalent in the spirit realm. Thus, a man lives at this point and his Chi at hand, meaning that a person is simply one half that is considered as the weaker half of that person. But there is Chi as the complementary spirit to the person (Achebe, 2014).

Thus, Abimbola (1975) opined that whatever has not been endorsed or approved by a person's Ori cannot be executed by the gods, and this means that Ori is the most important part of each person's nature. The Yoruba consider Ori as each person's personal guardian and god whose obligation it is to guard an individual and lead him to his selected destiny.

Ori: The Inner Head and Choice in Yoruba Thought

In Yoruba ontology, Ori as a word is used to designate the vessel that processes human conscious thought. Thus, in the *Ifa* explanation of Ori, consciousness is the mixing of thoughts and emotions. This amalgamation produces *ori ire* or wisdom (Fatunmbi, 2024). However, there is the physical and the spiritual aspects of Ori because in Yoruba thought, differentiation between *Ori-ode*, known as the physical head, and *Ori-inu* generally referred to as the spiritual/inner head). Nevertheless, the latter is the quintessence of personality and the

guardian or godparent of a person's path (Idowu, 1962).

Largely, Ori in the traditional Yoruba conviction, conveys a person's destiny, and defines the individual's personality. This implies that Ori in the Yoruba means the physical head, but in the metaphysical sense, this idea is considered as one of the elements that personifies an individual.

However, there is concealed what is called an intricate 'metaphysical duality' central to Yoruba belief. The complexity evolves from the idea that there is a corporal head (outer head), recognised as the *Ori-ode*, which is understood as the physical vessel or container for self and spirituality. There is the *Ori-inu*, referred to as the internal or spiritual head, and this forms the centre of a person's existence that is an embodiment of their individual destiny (Oluwaseun, 2025).

What Oluwaseun (2025) is stressing here is that *Ori-inu* exists before birth and survives the fleshly body. Thus, the relationship between the two Oris is somewhat hierarchal in the sense that the inner self appears to rule the outer; hence the Yorubas pray that the inner head should not spoil the outer one.

Chi: The Personalised Deity in Igbo Cosmology

In the Igbo worldview, Chi is the double or dual spirit, which, famously and appropriately, implies that anywhere something is standing, another thing is standing alongside it (Achebe, 1975). Thus, Chi is the thing that is standing

Advance Journal of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences

Adv. J. Arts. Hum. & Soc Sci.

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E-ISSN 4226-6348

Impact Factor: 7.80

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.net/ajahss/index.php/ajahss/index>

alongside, which derived from the Great Spirit called *Chukwu* who exists within the individual. Chi is a crucial concept of Igbo religious conviction that indicates a very dynamic indigenous cosmology. It basically has a dual characteristic and fluid, but not to be perceived as the Supreme Being. Rather, Chi is considered as the most potent unseen force, which the Igbo recognise as acting as a personal guiding spirit, (Eziju, 1992). In Igbo thought, every person is tied in a kind of contractual connexion with his or her Chi, which echoes in the proverb: If a person agrees, his or her Chi similarly agrees (*Onye kwe, Chi ya ekwe*). This suggests that by hard work, industry, and negotiation, a person can sway his or her destiny.

In effect, Achebe (1975) explains that the above can be interpreted as either the person has a principally stubborn and unyielding Chi or the person is endeavouring rather too late to change that primordial contract he or she had freely struck with his Chi.

Statement of the Problem

The Yoruba and Igbo cultures are often considered as communalistic because individuality is incorporated into the family and the clan, guided by unseen ethereal influences (Olugboji, 2021), and this suggests the cosmological thoughts of Ori (Yoruba) and Chi (Igbo); it suggests a deep and strong peculiar spiritual foundation.

It is observed that there is a link between the personal spiritual agents and the collective moral expectations and the spiritual. Thus, a

person's character, success, or failure is viewed as predestined and governed by a private spiritual being; this raises critical questions concerning the extent that a person is actually accountable for his or her moral failings. This raises further inquiries into whether a personal destiny can undermine existence or be determined and strengthened by such.

There is a need to examine how these notions are connected to a person's existence because without an understanding of the nature of Ori and Chi, it could be challenging to make logic of these Yoruba and Igbo world-view archetypes. No doubt, there exists body of works on these life philosophies, there is a need to juxtapose these concepts, understand further, and clearly compare them as a novel approach and addition to the earlier works and studies or discourse done by others in the areas.

Objective and Research Question

The study examines the means that Ori and Chi have influenced and swayed the development of individualism and moral responsibility within traditionally communal Yoruba and Igbo cultures. Consequently, the research question raised for this study is: In what ways do the personal nature of Ori and Chi influence the development of individualism and moral responsibility within traditionally communal Yoruba and Igbo societies?

Theoretical

Phenomenological Theory

The Phenomenological theory is propounded by Edmund Husserl and later refined by Maurice

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Merleau-Ponty and Alfred Schutz. It focuses on the logical study of human consciousness and the perception of life. The theory is an approach towards learning how people understand and appreciate the world. Thus, rather than looking for a truthful answer, the emphasis of this theory is on individual perspective, and it offers that truth is entrenched in the way an individual feels and reasons about their personal life-experiences. Hence, this theory is appropriate for studying, understanding, and appreciating spiritual notions, ideas or concepts, which are intrinsic and felt deep within, rather than viewed scientifically.

This theory examines Ori (Yoruba) and Chi (Igbo) as lived experiences about how individuals within these cultural contexts feel about how spirituality guides their lives, determines life-choices, and defines their identities daily.

Within their respective cultural contexts, Ori and Chi are believed to influence the Yoruba and Igbo people today as they are still entrenched in conversations and literatures. For that reason, phenomenology allows an understanding of how these cultural phenomena influence and sway the day-to-day existence and worldviews of individuals.

In the context of this study, phenomenology serves as the bridge between abstract cosmology and human reality. By focusing on the lived experiences of participants, the research explores how the concepts of Ori (Yoruba) and Chi (Igbo) are not just theoretical constructs,

but active forces that individuals perceive as shaping their destinies and identities.

Phenomenological Design within the Qualitative Approach

A phenomenological design (Ikenga-Metuh, 1984) was chosen to capture the essence of the perceptions and the needed fundamental ideas of Ori and Chi within the Yoruba and Igbo cultural milieu. Through this phenomenological method, in-depth, semi-structured interviews were conducted in order to get the multi-layered knowledge and perceptions of those that understands these spiritual concepts. Therefore, a purposive sampling technique was utilised in order to choose two key participants that are well-informed in these areas. These interviews ensured that all the research themes are covered and the data generated is examined through a thematic analysis.

Exploring Ori and Chi in their Cultural and Spiritual Contexts

This study involved in-depth interviews with two participants that are knowledgeable in Yoruba and Igbo cosmology. To protect their identities, they are referred to as Participant A (Yoruba tradition) and Participant B (Igbo tradition). Both participants are respected within their respective communities for their deep understanding of cultural concepts like Ori and Chi.

Conceptual Understanding

The primary role of Ori and Chi in an individual's life journey: Participant A, a Yoruba scholar and cultural expert, explained

that Yoruba concept of Ori, is much more than physical head, being the canister of personality and destiny, Ori is perceived as personal deity, that is why Ori is targeted in specific ceremonial activities for protection balance so that the individual always enjoy good mental health as *ìpín* (destiny) unfold as revealed by the oracle. On his own part, Participant B, an Igbo scholar and cultural expert explained that in the traditional understanding of Igbos, Chi is an individual's personal god who directs a person's life and this depends on how satisfied it is with the one concerned. On the Igbo concept of Chi, and in the Igbo culture, Chi is a philosophical, intense, and multifaceted concept that is roughly interpreted as "my personal god" or "my destiny." Chi is always understood to be a personal deity and peculiar; it is a spiritual being that guides and influences a person's life, including fate, and destiny. It has to do with a person's destiny, and is every so often connected to the person's predetermined life-route or life-destiny. The Igbos sees and believes Chi as the guardian spirit who functions as a guardian cum protector. Chi also influences decisions and outcomes, just as it impacts the individual identity that is exclusive to every person, modelling their character, strengths, traits, and weaknesses.

The role of Iwa (Yoruba) and Agwa (Igbo) in life: On this issue, Participant A stressed that a person's character is shaped by their upbringing, but nurtured by Iwa. Iwa is capable of making or marring person's *ìpín* (destiny).

Iwa serves as an anchor in fulfilling ones destiny. However, Participant B is of the opinion that Agwa is not determined by Chi, but formed from an individual's experiences and choices.

Individualism and Community

How Ori and Chi is unique and affect duty to the larger community: Participant A explains that every individual has an Ori that is personal or peculiar to them, that is why even a twin from same womb does not come with same *ìpín*, Taiye (first of the twins to arrive from the womb) can be a successful medical doctor, while Kehinde (second of the twins to arrive from the womb) could be a poor shoemaker. But, Participant B, on his part believes that the individual choses to be good or evil and Chi has nothing to do with his or her duty to the larger community. Chi is intertwined with Igbo values such as hard work, humility, and respect for tradition.

Ori and Chi as balance between personal effort and spiritual destiny: Participant A agreed that Ori is a reflection of one's destiny; the destiny and the body that carries it must work together for fulfilment. On this issue, Participant B opines that Chi agrees with choices made by the individual and rewards or punishes him accordingly.

Individual Moral Responsibility

Ori and Chi concerning crime or immoral act: Concerning this, Participant A said that committing a crime has nothing to do with Ori, it is upbringing, because for the mission of Ori

to become a fulfilment, the person must be an Omolúwàbí. Ìwà is sacrosanct in fulfilment of destiny (ìpín). Participant B explains that it is not necessarily so as the onus is on the person to be right and to do right.

Ori and Chi on personal failure and life path: Virtues of Omoluabi must be fulfilled to handle personal failure; this also underscores the saying *kí orí inú má bá tode ẹni jẹ́*. Ori inu is personal destiny, while Ori ode is personal behaviour which is ìwà Omoluabi. However, Participant B submitted that the individual remains responsible for every deliberate action. Chi has to do with personal accountability, and this view encourages folks to take ownership of their deeds and decisions.

Modern Relevance

Ori and Chi, personal destiny, and individual modern existence: According to Participant A, in Yoruba cosmology, akosejaye plays a vital role in knowing what the future holds, ifá plays a vital role in this aspect, after consultations one does not go to sleep, abiding and sticking to the dos and don'ts will help one in taking the ownership of one's life path. On his part, Participant B explained that personal failure could be confirmation that the person has opted to do the wrong or inappropriate things. The acceptance and belief in Chi inspires people to do what is good and be remunerated because Chi allows perceptions into the Igbo worldview. It highlights the complex connection between a person, spirituality, and community.

Effects of Ori and Chi on the Community:

On this matter, Participant A argued that the Abrahamic religion and modernism had permeated the concept of Ori and the many-sided problems that man faces nowadays is not unrelated with this. He added that "every one that comes to this world has individualistic mission, based on their Ori. Someone who has been destined to die young will not be old, those who are been destined to be rich will find means of being rich without much stress." He explained further that the society and societal values will always be a common wealth, but destiny is personal. Participant B clarified that the Chi thought is inconsistent or not in tandem with Christianity; for example, which expounds the grace and mercy of God through Jesus Christ. He added that "as a Christian, the idea was made-believe in order to serve the purpose of instilling social order, and it is much distant from truth and reality".

Thematic Analysis of Interview Data

A thematic analysis of the interview data provides vital insights into the concepts of Ori and Chi. Thus, in that regard, the emerging themes have been identified through a careful examination of the responses from the two participants, thereby highlighting the commonalities and variances in their understandings.

1. The Concept of Personal Deity (Ori versus Chi)

Both participants agree that the concepts of Ori and Chi indicate more than "providence"; these

are personal deities that are personal or individualistic that act as a kind of plan for a person's existence. Participant A (Yoruba) stresses the double nature of Ori, which are the physical or corporeal head (Ori Ode) and the other is the spiritual destiny (Ori Inu). He regarded it as a vessel of personality that demands ritual alignment in order to guarantee mental wellbeing and destiny (Ipin).

Participant B (Igbo) defined Chi as a personal and peculiar god that guides the life of the individual. Remarkably, he observed that while it is a guardian, its guidance is intensely tied to the person's choices.

2. Personal Agency and Divine Destiny

The two Participants did not accept the fatalistic view on this where the person is an ordinary puppet. The concepts of Iwa and Agwa (Character) in both cultures are associated to the weight of success on the character. Participant A used the idea of the woman "throwing away her character" as an indication that bad and depraved behaviour can affect a good destiny. Participant B appeared to be more direct by asserting that Agwa (character) is moulded by choices and experiences; not by the Chi.

However, there is a remarkable similarity in the negotiation with the divine as Participant A asserted that in Yoruba, one must be a person of virtue (Omoluabi) for Ori's undertaking to noticeable. But Participant B opined that in Igbo, Chi agrees or aligns with the person's

choices, thus if the person say yes, his or her Chi says yes as well.

3. Moral Responsibility and Social Accountability

Concerning the blame on the spirit for crimes, this generated a common position from both Participants. This is because they both agree on individual liability as they both asserted that committing a crime is an offshoot of a failed upbringing or the outcome of personal choice, and not a dictate of Ori or Chi. Thus, based on community standards, the concept of the Omoluabi (Yoruba) serves as the bridge, and a person's personal destiny remains valid if only it exists within the context of moral integrity.

4. Influence of Modernity and Religion

There is a minor divergence on this area as the two participants are of the view that religion has permeated human existence and this is in conflict with the concepts of Ori and Chi. Participant A saw the neglect of Ori as a reason for current many-sided problems, and this suggests a dislodgment of spiritual alignment of man and the concepts.

Participant B takes a further sceptical stance as he argued that the concept of Chi could have been a social construct that is created in order to preserve order, thereby viewing it as inconsistent with the belief of grace.

Findings

1. Yoruba Ori is described as the vessel of personality and a personal deity (Orisha) that needs preservation through rituals in order to

Advance Journal of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences

Adv. J. Arts. Hum. & Soc Sci.

Volume: 9; Issue: 02

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ISSN 6300-5290

E-ISSN 4226-6348

Impact Factor: 7.80

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.net/ajahss/index.php/ajahss/index>

guarantee mental wellbeing and good destiny.

The Igbo Chi is considered as a personal god or guardian spirit that acts as a spiritual double, which validates a person's path.

2. A notable finding is that destiny is not tantamount to fatalism, based on Participant A's submission that character (Iwa) is the anchor, even as a good Ori, bad character can ruin an individual's destiny. Participant B highlighted the fact that the Igbo agency that espouses that if a person says yes, his Chi also says yes. The Chi is sensitive to a person's struggles and it supports the direction that the person chooses to follow.

3. Both participants agree that immoral deeds cannot be attributed to Ori or Chi because in Yoruba belief, a criminal falls short of being an Omoluabi (ideal person), and In Igbo worldview, the person remains accountable for the determined action. Thus, failure is observed to be lack of alignment between the inner head and outer behaviour; it is a sign that the Chi is displeased with the person's decisions.

4. There is a divergence of opinion on how the two participants perceive the adaptation of these concepts to the contemporary period. Participant A said that Abrahamic religions subvert these concepts of Ori and Chi, due to their many problems. It is observed that

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Participant B, speaking from a Christian perspective, viewed the concept of Chi as a invented tool deployed for social order, thereby suggesting that Christianity has made the traditional belief to be out-dated in some aspects of life.

Conclusion

Ori and Chi are metaphysical frameworks well-designed for individual accountability. They are prearranged spiritual plan (ipin/destiny) that places the life-compass in the hands of human beings through Iwa (character) and Agwa (behavior). While there is a tenuous connection of these concepts with modernity, the Yoruba perspective strives for a return to these ideas in order to sustain mental and spiritual balance. The Igbo viewpoint indicates a greater degree of pressure because the Christian doctrine often views Chi as a primordial concept that leverages on modernism.

Recommendations

There is a need to integrate and reinforce the concepts of Ori and Chi with personal responsibility as a way of shifting from the usual blame on the devil attitudes regularly found in modern religions. However, there is a necessity for further comparative studies on how the concepts of Ori and Chi affect gender roles and stereotyping.

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Advance Journal of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences

Adv. J. Arts. Hum. & Soc. Sci.

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Advance Journal of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences

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